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**COMPARISON OF THE AZERBAIJANI EDUCATION SYSTEM WITH THE US
EDUCATION SYSTEM
(XX-XXI CENTURIES (1960-2015))**

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Abstract: The educational reforms implemented in our country, first of all, require the establishment of a system of pedagogical sciences at the level of world standards. Whether in the education reform program, in the materials related to the concept of education, or in the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Education" (2009) it is important to form the worldview of the rising generation with reference to the history of school and pedagogical thought are considered conditions. These documents recommend the humanization, humanization and democratization of education as the most necessary factor. For this, it is impossible to succeed without comparing the educational process in our country with the educational process in our modern world. Therefore, the improvement of the content of education in our country is conditioned by the study and research of comparative pedagogy. At the same time, there is an opportunity to compare the Azerbaijani education system with the education systems of developed countries and benefit from them.

The study of the structure, problems and pedagogical conditions of overcoming the problems of the world education systems, and the generalizations made in this case, the proposed provisions will enrich our pedagogical thinking, as well as increase the outlook of students and educators.

The article reflects the research conducted in various areas related to the education system of developed countries (mainly the American education system). These studies cover the history of education in advanced and neighboring countries, its content, structure, management, admission rules, assessment models, etc. reflects the rich material on.

Keywords: Education system, American education system, teacher training, innovative approaches in education

The foundation of the Azerbaijani education system was laid in the third century AD. Thus, during this period, there were separate schools in Azerbaijan that provided basic literacy training.

Due to the spread of Islam in Azerbaijan, the education system was significantly improved and was widespread in many cities of that time. It is known that the application of Islam in Azerbaijan has played an important role in the development of science. The emergence of prominent thinkers and scientists in various fields of science, both in the East and in Azerbaijan, is due to the broad conditions created by Islamic culture. The parallel development of science and education in Azerbaijan coincides with this period. Tabriz, Maragha, Ganja, Nakhchivan, Shamakhi, Hamadan, Ardabil and other cities became literally centers of science and culture in the X-XIII centuries. It should be noted that education was not widespread at that time. This education, which covered only a certain segment of the population, was also paid. Evliya Chalabi, a Turkish traveler who visited Azerbaijan in the middle of the 17th century, noted that in 1647 there were 47 secondary schools, 600 primary schools in Tabriz alone, 7 secondary schools and 40 primary schools in Shamakhi (Stenographic report of the XI Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers, 1999). The education system was developing in the same way in other cities of Azerbaijan..

It should be noted that in the Middle Ages, higher education institutions were widespread in Azerbaijan. Universities, observatories and libraries operating in Ganja, Shamakhi, Beylagan, Nakhchivan, Barda, Tabriz, Maragha were famous all over the world. Darulfu, the first higher education institution in the Near and Middle East, was also considered a major scientific center in the West. Founded in the 15th century

in Tabriz, the university had about 7,000 students, most of them Azerbaijanis.

The rapid development of the education system in the following periods dates back to the twenty-first century. At present, there are 4481 educational institutions covering the education system in the country. 1 million in educational institutions of the Ministry of Education 325 thousand 634 students, 175 thousand 538 teachers work (shorthand report of the XV Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers, 2018).

The achievements of our people in the field of education are great. Indeed, the path taken proves once again that the quality of education is the common cultural foundation of the nation. The implementation of general compulsory secondary education in Azerbaijan is enshrined in the Constitution of our republic.

Improving the content of educational work in the field of education is of great importance. Recently, some work has been done to improve the quality of education, to maintain and further increase the achievements in the field of education. Although the western education system, especially in the United States, has had some success compared to the current education system, reforms in education since independence and the creation of new private schools show that much remains to be done.

Among the problems facing society in the United States is the desire to achieve a perfect education for every child. The journal USA: Society and Values (U.S. Society & Values, 2000) focuses on this issue, noting that the concept of a perfect education includes the high responsibility of students, parents, schools, teachers and the local community. That is, the above-mentioned contingent should not shy away from the process of educating the child.

US Secretary of Education Arn Duncan believes that the creation and operation of strong schools is the foundation of America. There is some truth in this opinion. The development of education in any society shows the true face of that society, the direction of development. In this regard, the care and attention to education in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which has embarked on the path to independence, and its development at the state level is commendable.

The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan pays special attention to the development of education. The Minister of Education Mikayil Jabbarov touched upon this issue in his report to the XIV Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers and praised the activities of the President in this field. It should be noted that the speeches of US President Barack Obama also reflected the development of the American education system.

According to Obama, despite the very important challenges facing the US education system, we must continue to provide access to education for all students. In general, experience shows that states that pay attention to the development of education in the country, heads of state correctly understand that it is a powerful tool in the overall progress of society. In this regard, it is commendable that special attention has been paid to the development of the education system in Azerbaijan since independence. Today, the most urgent task is to update the content and quality of training and education in the field of education. The main task facing the workers of the education system is to cultivate this important field in accordance with the history, morality and traditions of our people, to raise and form a new generation that will be able to effectively use the vast opportunities provided by our independence for the benefit of the people and state.

Education must constantly contribute to the development of the country, as well as its citizens. The American educator C.M. Theodore pays special attention to the development of these qualities of education in society. According to him, the education system must be constantly updated and rebuilt in accordance with the requirements of the time.

The American education system has been affected in this way for the last 70 years. After the Second World War, the education system in this country was rebuilt and significantly expanded. In particular, the country's higher education system has undergone more changes in this regard. Education is more open and inclusive, more equitable and more responsive to the needs of society. At present, higher education in this country is treated as an integral part of building the capacity of the skilled labor force.

Another American expert, William Peters, analyzed the state of the education system in the country and concluded that over the past 25 years, the number of American students in college and university admissions on standardized tests has been steadily declining. Interestingly, some experts see this as a manifestation of the shortcomings of the US education system (What Matters Most, 2013).

Undoubtedly, the American education system has more advanced traditions than the Azerbaijani education system. We must take into account that the test system has been applied in Azerbaijan since independence and has its own advantages and disadvantages. The long-term application of the test system in the West, especially in the United States, has already led to significant improvements in this area. However, American experts still note that there are certain shortcomings in the education system with the introduction of the test. Undoubtedly, some improvements are being made in this direction in Azerbaijan as well, and the experience gained in the world practice, including in-depth study of the US education system, is being used at

the required level.

When creating a state, it puts before itself the implementation of important directions, new ideas that ensure its development, and strives for their implementation. US Secretary of Education Arn Duncan points out that the United States is facing such important ideas. Highly appreciating the role of education in the development of the state, Arn Duncan said that one of the ideas that this new democratic state hoped for when creating the United States was to educate all citizens and educate people for society. The first presidents of the United States, including Thomas Jefferson, as well as other statesmen, wanted both processes to go hand in hand, focusing on the intellectual and spiritual development of man. According to them, in a country where the government belongs to the people, the tendency to education contributes to the development of democracy and acts as a catalyst for future progress.

This demand for education, interest has stood the test of time. For more than two centuries, the US education system has been thriving. However, this system is constantly changing and improving in accordance with the requirements of the time. For example, in the 1950s and 1960s, the proportion of skilled workers in the United States was 20 percent, and the number of unskilled workers was 60 percent. That is, today the number of skilled workers among the working people has reached 60 percent, and the number of unskilled workers has reached 20 percent. So, in connection with the development of the scientific and technological revolution in society, the constant education of people is becoming an important problem of the day. People can lose their jobs if they do not keep up with the demands of the times.

The same situation is manifested not in the United States, but in almost all countries of the modern world. In Azerbaijan itself, new sectors of the economy require the specialization of workers. Today, as new jobs are created, the problem of employees being educated in accordance with their specialization also arises. This means that people's literacy will increase steadily and will set new tasks for the society's education system.

It is no coincidence that US President Barack Obama called the 21st century the "century of education." According to him, the living standards of the population depend on how many educated, capable and competent citizens there are in the country.

The American education system considers it very important to create an environment that allows people to acquire knowledge independently. Such an environment will allow an 8-year-old student to learn to read in this country, every 12-year-old schoolboy to acquire the skills to work in the Internet, every 18-year-old to enter college, and finally every adult to continue their education throughout their lives.

In the process of education, when children are faced with certain tasks, their tastes and interests must be taken into account. Fulfilling this requirement will allow them to acquire more knowledge.

One of the main conditions for children's success in the learning process is the establishment of strict discipline in teaching. Experience has shown that when strict discipline is applied, every child acquires the basics of both reading and mathematical knowledge. Of course, one of the main conditions here is that parents, teachers and students have the means to determine the level of knowledge.

Children must be able to work mentally. They need to create and shape this ability in the process of daily work. If children are not required to do mental work, they may quickly lose interest in learning, miss classes, and usually have few opportunities, which will have a negative impact on their future success. For example, in the fourth year of study, students who cannot read independently and solve the simplest mathematical problems, and in the eighth year who have no idea about more complex subjects such as algebra and geometry, will have limited life choices. Because this fundamental knowledge acquired in high school helps to master the curriculum in the process of preparation, which is necessary to enter this or that university. Today, high demands are placed on pupils, students and teachers. In order for learners to acquire knowledge, they must be able to use the most accurate technologies. In the United States, as well as in developed countries, students have no difficulty in using the latest technologies. Because the curriculum includes teaching the latest technologies to students starting from secondary schools. In a number of developed countries, children are still taught the latest technologies in preschools.

In the United States, the teaching of highly qualified teachers in every classroom is a constant focus on creating a safe environment in schools, the absence of drugs, and the ability of hard-working and well-educated students to attend colleges. Parents, other family members and community members are actively involved in school life.

Great attention is paid to reading in US schools. This is considered the main foundation. Because the whole subsequent life of a student depends on his ability to read.

It is known that at all times, rulers, kings and emperors obstructed the development of schools and the involvement of the masses in education in order to keep the people in slavery and to slow down the intellectual development of the population, to prevent education. The most reactionary regimes have always subjugated

newspapers, television and radio, closed libraries and burned these rich spiritual treasures. In civilized countries, however, speech, education, and, in general, the increase in the literacy of the population have always been respected.

The Reading America program is well developed in the United States (U.S. Society & Values, 2014). The main goal of this program is to mobilize all Americans to build long-term partnerships with teachers, educators, and school-loyal citizens at every school and library in the country, thereby strengthening teaching and learning institutions and, ultimately, helping children become independent in their third year. to ensure that they can read. One of the areas of work of this program is the involvement of qualified guardians who pay extra attention to those who need to work with students and teachers.

However, this program is not enough, it does not fully cover the entire student body. Thus, the US National Education Level Assessment Program shows that 40 percent of fourth-graders in this country have not mastered basic reading skills. With this in mind, President Obama has proposed conducting voluntary national reading tests for fourth-graders. These tests provide participating schools with a powerful new tool for improving students' reading skills, which can help parents, teachers and supervisors determine children's ability to read, as well as help them determine their level of knowledge. When teaching reading, it is possible to set specific goals and identify specific indicators.

In Azerbaijan, the test method is already used in primary school, especially in the fourth grade, but in the future, the use of this practice will become one of the current tasks of teaching.

The study of mathematics and the natural sciences, one of the main subjects in secondary schools in the United States, is also in focus. Recent documents released by the US Department of Education show that there is a direct correlation between students taking an extensive math course and passing their college entrance exams, as well as their success in the subsequent learning process.

It is very important to pay high attention to the main subjects. At the same time, it is very important to achieve the application of the latest teaching systems and the effective use of the latest technical means in the acquisition of knowledge. Various forms of computers and telecommunications technology are an important part of well-organized training. Such technical means created in schools, universities, master's programs are important in the acquisition of basic and specialized knowledge.

Special attention should be paid to the technology of teaching, the provision of universities with various types of technical means. US President Barack Obama always draws attention to these aspects of education. The budget recently approved by him also envisages huge investments in teaching technology. Undoubtedly, these investments will expand students' access to knowledge and allow teachers to use computers and other new technical means in their teaching.

Certain funds are allocated from the budget for the development of education in Azerbaijan. Unfortunately, due to the small amount of these funds today, the provision of schools and universities with new technical equipment is not at the desired level. Although the process of equipping individual companies and institutions with technical means is weak, in any case, the gap in this area is gradually being filled. It is hoped that in the future, high-level work in this area in Azerbaijan will not escape the attention of government agencies, as well as various companies and departments.

Just as high school and college students in the United States are good at using computers and the Internet, so are students in Azerbaijan who are good at using computers and the Internet. However, children and young people studying in our secondary and higher education institutions are not fully covered by technical means. U.S. students can access world-class libraries and museums with these tools, take advantage of the latest and most advanced teaching methods, and receive specific information about any field. Teacher work is hard but honorable work. When this labor time is valued by the state and the public, it has a rich social nature.

In the United States, a presidential decree has allocated the necessary funds for the issuance of "Exemplary Teacher" certificates to 100,000 teachers. These calculations were made in such a way that every American school could have at least one such teacher, because it is very important to have such a teacher at school. The activities of those who have been named "exemplary teachers" will be an example for other teachers, convincing them that the teaching profession has a wide range of opportunities.

Recently, there has been a lot of talk in our country about the fact that teachers are allegedly moving away from schools due to economic difficulties. Taking this into account, the Minister of Education Mikayil Jabbarov clarified this issue at the XIV Congress of Teachers. If we look at the statistics, we can see that the number of teachers has not decreased, as shown above, but has increased significantly. Thus, a transparent, objective and flexible mechanism has been created for the widespread use of ICT in the field of teacher recruitment. As a result of the centralized competition, 1692 teachers were hired in 2014, 1405 of them (83%

of those hired) started working in rural schools and incentives were applied to young specialists. Compared to the previous school year, the level of vacancies has increased by 40 percent (Shorthand report of the XV Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers, 2018).

In order to further improve the staffing of rural schools, the Ministry of Education has prepared and submitted to the Government proposals to increase the amount of incentives for young professionals. "On the establishment of additional benefits and incentives for young professionals who have graduated and started working in general education institutions" (Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan Resolution No. 67 of April 14, 2010 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan. According to the decision, according to the state order, young professionals under the age of 35 who start working in general education institutions and continue to work in that educational institution for 3 years are compensated in the amount of 60 (sixty) manat to pay for utilities and accommodation. Young specialists starting their careers in general education institutions located more than 20 km away from the district centers are paid an additional 100 (one hundred) manats per month for 3 years. One of the important innovations envisaged in the decision was that after the expiration of the 3-year period, 10 young professionals continuing their pedagogical activities in one or another rural school are paid compensation and additional salaries for another 2 years. As a result of systematic work by the Ministry of Education on teacher recruitment, new mechanisms and incentives, the need for teaching staff in rural schools has been minimized and the number of vacancies in the country after the last competition is less than 1% of the total number of teachers.

In accordance with the relevant Order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan to stimulate the activities of secondary schools and teachers, competitions "Best Secondary School" and "Best Teacher" were held, 50 schools and 100 teachers were awarded and awarded in the prescribed manner. In general, in 2008-2015, the number of awarded teachers reached 700, and the number of schools reached 350.

It should be noted that the situation in our country is better than in developed countries due to the number of students who are responsible for teachers. At the XIV Teachers' Congress, the Minister of Education paid special attention to this issue and said: "... While in developed countries there are about 20-30 students per teacher, in our country there are 8 students per teacher" (Stenographic report of the XV Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers, 2018). It is important to note that in 2015, for the first time, a test assessment of the knowledge and skills of 60,000 teachers working in secondary schools and some regions of Baku was conducted. The main purpose of the assessment was to determine the level of knowledge and skills of teachers, to develop training programs and organize trainings to improve their professionalism, to stimulate the activities of teachers who have achieved high results. This assessment was of exceptional importance in terms of preparation for teacher certification and was a reliable source of concrete steps to be taken to improve the professionalism of teachers. Draft agreements agreed between the Ministries of Education, Finance and Labor and Social Protection to increase the weekly workload of teachers conducting diagnostic assessments of knowledge and skills by 1.5 times and the monthly salary by 2 times since 2015 have been submitted to the Cabinet of Ministers.

Every school in the United States is required to ensure that the level of education meets the highest quality standards. If any school is unable to provide students with the necessary knowledge, the school is closed or appropriate work is done to improve the quality of education there. Here, inspectors and school councils have great responsibilities. They should be ready to change school principals if necessary.

The US education system has had some success in this area. The new corporation of American schoolchildren has made great strides in applying the methods of successful schools to all regions, thereby reviving local schools. It is already known what reforms will bring good results in schoolwork. Therefore, if necessary, these reforms should be carried out in schools, or certain methods of work should be applied.

Building the education system on a new basis and acquiring a new quality does not depend only on the increase in public funding for education. But it should be noted that the role of this factor is great.

American schools pay great attention to the participation of citizens in the life of educational institutions. It is believed that this factor is the most powerful tool to increase the efficiency of schools.

Taking this factor into account, government agencies pay great attention to the role of parents, other family members, businesspeople, and the community in the development of the education system. They have even taken some important steps to organize the voluntary participation of citizens in school life. As a rule, the use of private business in US schools in family and school-related activities to improve the quality of education has been resolved. The use of private business makes school staff more interested in their professions and gives children a better education. For this purpose, purposeful work must be done to encourage businessmen and wealthy people to invest in the school.

Successful steps must be taken in this area in Azerbaijan as well. It is impossible to raise the quality

of education, material and technical base to any level with the funds allocated by the state alone. The experience of the United States, as well as other Western countries, in this area should be used effectively. Much remains to be done to attract individual businessmen, businessmen and various companies operating in Azerbaijan to finance education. Experience shows that when family members and school staff work with pupils and students, new opportunities, new incentives and new tools emerge in the field of children's knowledge acquisition.

This method has worked in US schools. Thus, well-mastered subjects create new perspectives for students in the field of education, as private companies pay special attention to the connection of school classes to the Internet, volunteering with the remaining students and participation in various forms of work. Such an approach increases the amount of success and achievements in teaching.

U.S. educators have seen a significant increase in students' knowledge (in mathematics and science) in recent years in the successful application of this method.

US Secretary of Education Arn Duncan called the move a turning point in the public education system. "We have not yet achieved the desired result, but we are on the right track," he said. The public, families and private enterprises have begun to take an active part in the life of schools and are striving to strengthen them. But we also need to control the prevention of addiction to miraculous solutions, which are, in fact, useless political movements that only isolate us from each other. "(Changing educational landscapes: educational policies, schooling systems and higher education: a comparative perspective, selected papers from the 23rd CESE conference. Edited by Dimitris Mattheou, 2010, 328 p.).

Education in the United States is one of the key factors in the development of the state. It is no coincidence that the report, published by the country's Commission on Pedagogical Activity and the Future of America, sees knowledge as the key to the success and even survival of nations and peoples. The commission's report rightly states that "in today's society, there is almost no place for those who cannot read, write, calculate quickly, discover and take advantage of resources, as well as master new technologies, new habits and professions." The US Secretary of Education praises the President's care for education. "President Obama understands the great role that education will play in the future accomplishments and actions of every citizen of our powerful country," he said. By striving not only to continue but also to increase the traditional focus of our people on education, we will be able to contribute to a bright future for all our people and for each individual. "

The current reforms in the field of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan are aimed at ensuring a bright future for every citizen in our country, increasing the role of every person in the development of society. Today, Azerbaijan is conducting effective research in the field of education.

It is a reality that the development of countries in modern times can be achieved only through education. World experience shows that the level of development of any state is determined not by the abundance of the country's natural resources, but by the transformation of these resources into human capital with high potential.

In this regard, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, said with great foresight: "We must turn our material values and economic potential into human capital. Oil and gas are great blessings from God, and we use them successfully and skillfully. But sooner or later, these natural resources will be depleted, and knowledge, intelligence and level will ensure the sustainable development of our country for many years to come. If we look at the experience of the most developed countries, we can see that the leading role in the development of those countries is not oil and gas, but knowledge, scientific and technological progress, new technologies. " (Shorthand report of the XV Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers. Baku, 2018. - 14 p.) - This requirement is based on the conceptual idea, the main strategic goal of the modern education system.

A draft Action Plan for the implementation of the "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan" (State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku, 2013) approved by the Presidential Decree No. 13 of October 24, 2013 was prepared and submitted to the Government. The Action Plan reflects concrete measures to achieve the goals set out in the Strategy in order to build a competitive education system in accordance with the development concept of Azerbaijan and best international practice.

In 2014, at the initiative of the Ministry of Education, a number of important steps were taken to promote education. For the first time in the field of higher education, the project of SABAH (literate, skilled, prepared) groups has been launched. 769 people in 33 specialty groups from 34 higher education institutions were selected on the basis of three-stage competition and admitted to SABAH groups. These groups began to operate with the application of special programs and modern teaching technologies, intensive foreign language

teaching, and the involvement of professional teachers. These groups are intended to train educated, skilled, trained and competitive specialists who will contribute to the development of Azerbaijan.

In order to participate in exchange programs of students studying in "SABAH" groups, to teach some subjects of vocational training in some specialties in English, to invite teachers from abroad to teach English, as well as vocational training, to provide students with in-depth practical knowledge and future career. It is planned to establish close relations with large companies, committees, ministries of the republic, as well as foreign companies, provide low-income students from the regions with accommodation and meals, and provide "SABAH" scholarships to students studying on a state order and paid basis.

In accordance with the “State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan”, the Ministry of Education has started to develop e-learning resources within the informatization of education, www.e-derslik.edu.az, www.e-sinif.edu.az, www.e-telim.edu.az, www.e-test.edu.az, www.i-olimp.edu.az have been launched. The development of an electronic examination system www.imtahan.edu.az has begun, through which it will be possible to assess and certify people working in the field of education. E-learning resources have opened up a wide range of opportunities to improve the quality, modernize the national education system and adapt it to best international practices, and provide teachers, students and parents with access to e-resources.

In 2014, the universities participated in Tempus and Erasmus Mundus programs to learn best international practices and exchange faculty. At present, 25 projects selected by the European Commission are being implemented by universities in our country. The Ministry of Education participates in 9 Tempus projects as a partner. More than 500 professors and administrators of Azerbaijani universities have participated in Tempus-funded trainings, study tours, seminars and other events. 668 students, researchers and faculty benefited from the Erasmus Mundus program.

The draft “State Program for the Development of Inclusive Education for Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2015-2022” prepared with the technical support of UNICEF was prepared and submitted to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The goal of the program is to ensure the involvement of people with disabilities in education at all levels of education and to create a barrier-free environment for them to receive an education. Mrs. Mehriban Aliyeva, President of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, Goodwill Ambassador of UNESCO and ISESCO, who has made a worthy contribution to educational reforms and development of education in the country, said at a recent ceremony in Paris on the occasion of the 20th anniversary of Azerbaijan's accession to UNESCO. We have paid special attention to the development and modernization of the system. We firmly believe that only a country with a high level of education can succeed and provide a better quality of life for its people,” he said. We believe that the signing of the Framework Agreement on Cooperation in Education, Science, Culture and Communication between UNESCO and the Government of Azerbaijan on July 18 this year as a continuation of large-scale projects implemented in the education system at the initiative of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation is a strong impetus for a new stage in education reform in Azerbaijan. will give.

As you know, as Azerbaijan has completed the transition period in the economic sphere, the Development Concept "Azerbaijan 2020: Vision for the Future" ("Azerbaijan 2020: Vision for the Future" Development Concept, 2011) has been prepared. Approved by the Order dated 2012. This historical document envisages laying the foundation for the transition from a traditional economy to a "knowledge economy" and prioritizing the adequate development of human capital, which is a crucial factor for this. This leads to a radical change in the education system, increasing the importance of components such as additional education, lifelong learning. At the same time, it envisages increasing the role of ICT and virtual education, computer network knowledge. Improving the quality of education and building a modern education system are also highlighted as one of the key strategic directions in the Concept, whose main strategic goal is sustainable economic growth and social welfare.

The creative application of the advantages and achievements of the leading countries of the world, including the United States, to the reality of Azerbaijan opens up new prospects for the development of our education system as a whole.

However, it should be noted that the US education system has not suddenly reached today's level. The education system in this country has developed almost rapidly since the Second World War. Listing the achievements, especially in the postwar period, the vice-president of the American Higher Education Association, J. Marchis Theodore, noted that half a century ago, a well-developed higher education system was established in America. At that time, about 1.5 million students were studying in 1,700 colleges across the country.

The United States made major changes in education and almost rebuilt the system after World War

II. Over the past 70 years, major reforms have been made in the education system. If we look at the history of the development of education after the war, we can see that the development of the education system in the United States was mainly influenced by three important factors.

In 1944, the US government passed a law on the rights of soldiers. Under the law, the government took responsibility for the education of deported soldiers in colleges and vocational schools. Therefore, countless soldiers returning from the war preferred higher education. This process continued until the 1950s.

The second factor in the development of education occurred in 1947. Thus, the commission on war veterans, who have already received higher education, made a proposal that the necessary opportunities should be created for these young people.

The third important factor is the growing interest in science in the United States after the war. Thus, in 1945, based on the military interests of the country, Bush noted that investment in science is never lost, it brings huge benefits to national security and social development.

Soon, the number of scientists working to increase the military-industrial complex, the country's defense capabilities began to grow. They gained new scientific achievements by working in government agencies and university laboratories.

The establishment of the National Science Foundation by the US Congress in 1950 opened up great prospects for the study of fundamental and applied sciences. That same year, more than \$ 1 billion was allocated from the federal budget for scientific research. In the following years, the amount of these funds increased year by year and covered a very large part of the federal budget. So, in 2006, these funds were \$ 21 billion. 95% of this amount was directed to the development of science in more than 100 higher education institutions.

The real revival in the US higher education system took place in the 1960s. Experts attribute this to the emergence of a new generation after World War II. This generation was more interested in education than their parents. Thus, from 1960 to 1970, the number of students in the United States increased from 3.6 million to 8 million. Expenditures on education increased from \$ 5.8 billion to \$ 21.5 billion. To meet the educational needs of so many young people who want to study, colleges and universities have expanded their activities, and federal funds and private institutions that spend on education have also begun to make the most of their opportunities and increase their sponsorship of education (Schriewer J., Holmes B. Theories and methods in comparative education., 1992).

By the way, we can see an analogue of this development in every allied republic that is part of the former USSR, including Azerbaijan. Thus, we can also note that in our country in the 60s and 70s there was a great revival in the field of education. After the young people who returned after the Second World War got married, their children, the new generation, the young people of the 60s, entered higher education. This generation's need for life, interest in education, and inclination were completely different from those of previous decades. In order to meet the educational needs of these young people in Azerbaijan, as in the United States, the number of universities increased, the system was expanded, and new educational institutions began to operate.

This policy has also been implemented in the construction of secondary schools and preschools. Thus, as a result of the far-sighted, purposeful policy pursued in the field of education at that time, the number of preschool institutions was increased from 1,600 to 1,875, and 680 secondary schools with more than 350,000 places were built and put into operation. In addition, the greatest success of our education system during that period was the gradual transition from 8-year education to compulsory secondary education. At the same time, the increase in vocational schools has not gone unnoticed. During that period, the number of vocational schools increased from 84 to 173, and the number of students increased from 44,000 to 120,000 (Aliyev Heydar. Speech at the First Youth Forum of the Independent Republic of Azerbaijan. "Azerbaijan" newspaper, February 6, 1999).

The establishment of five new universities in the country in the 60s and 70s and the strengthening of the material and technical base of educational institutions at all levels also attracts attention as a manifestation of the state's care for the education system. After Azerbaijan gained independence, this progressive tradition continues today. At present, our young people are successfully studying not only in Russia, the United States, Great Britain, France and Japan, but also in universities in Turkey, Iran, China, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Romania, Poland and Egypt.

In the 1960s, a new type of educational institution emerged in the United States - general education colleges. These four educational institutions gave bachelor's degrees, replacing the preparatory colleges that appeared at the beginning of the work. When these institutions were established, they were intended to be in close contact with the public, to be freely admitted, and to ensure a high status of vocational education. Soon,

all regions of the country expressed their desire to create such colleges that are suitable for everyone. About 500 colleges were opened in the country in a short time. The number of students studying in these educational institutions increased from 453,000 to 2.2 million. Specialists in various professions were trained in these educational institutions. One of the advantages of the newly established colleges was that if factories and enterprises in any part of the country needed a specialist in one profession or another, those colleges immediately took into account this need and provided training in a short period of time. By taking this step, these educational institutions kept pace with real life and participated in the training of specialists in specific professions.

With the rapid expansion of the education network in the United States, as well as the emergence of new educational institutions, there was a need for some changes in the planning, management and funding mechanisms. With this in mind, in the 1960s, commissions were set up to manage and coordinate education, as well as to monitor the planned growth of higher education institutions. According to the US Department of Education, the master plan, developed by Clark Kerr in California in 1960, has become a nationally acclaimed model. The plan was to select approximately 12 percent of the best high school graduates from all of California's high schools and place them at the University of California. Of course, the university could not afford to accept so many students. Therefore, the issue of expanding the university was an important task. Soon, 9 campuses were built in California. The bulk of these universities' four-year education costs were determined by the state. This financial work was carried out as follows. One-third of the budget was funded by the state and one-third by student tuition. This progressive method should be used in our republic as well.

In the United States, the issue of meeting the social needs of students is in the center of attention. As far back as the 1960s and 1970s, there was a consensus that targeted federal programs aimed at creating equal opportunities for students to receive federal aid and education should be discontinued, regardless of their origin.

The Higher Education Act of 1965 in the United States laid the foundation for a modern system of financial aid for students. This law was amended in 1972. Thus, the law provides for all financial assistance, employment opportunities, and loans to help students get an education and provide a living wage while in college. The most important aspect of this law is that the amount of financial assistance that a student can receive is determined by taking into account the family income and the cost of college education.

Educational institutions in the United States take into account the economic and social changes taking place in the country. The education system has made great strides in this area. The issue of creating equal opportunities in education has already been resolved. In other words, in the past (1950) women made up a quarter of students, but now their share in education has reached 55 percent. This is very different from other countries. Thus, 10 percent of students are women in Africa, 7 percent in Latin America and 6 percent in Asia.

The US education system has some distinctive features. At present, 15 million people study at 3,700 higher education institutions in the country, which also costs more than \$ 200 billion. It should be noted that in the UK, these costs are equal to 0.9%. There are so many large universities in the United States that there are between 35,000 and 50,000 students. Such universities employ 4,000 teachers and 10,000 service staff, with a personal donation of \$ 150 million a year. The value of the funds of such a university reaches \$ 1 billion.

There are also some differences in the way tuition is paid in public and private colleges in the United States. Thus, the annual tuition fee for a four-year state college is \$ 3,000, and for a private college - \$ 13,000.

It should be noted that this difference is also reflected in the public and private universities operating in Azerbaijan. The introduction of fee-based education in public higher education institutions is not higher than that of many private institutions, but lower. But it is also true that tuition fees are low at some private schools.

What is the difference between tuition fees in state and private colleges in the United States?

The difference between tuition fees in this country is due to the fact that private colleges are deprived of direct state support. Seeing such differences in tuition fees, some observers have suggested that the private sector is failing. However, we are witnessing the development of Western countries, as well as prestigious private colleges and universities in the United States. It is impossible to agree with the idea that the private sector is doomed to bankruptcy. Experience shows that as the material and technical base of the private sector strengthens, so does their prestige. In the United States, 78 percent of students currently study in the private sector. Private higher education is becoming more perfect and oriented to modern values.

There are also some differences between the subjects taught in private and public colleges. Although students receive a bachelor's degree in both education systems, there are some differences between the subjects taught to them. Each college or educational institution is independent in developing and implementing the

curriculum. During the four-year period, students spend one-third of their time on special subjects, one-third on auxiliary subjects, and the remaining third on general education for two years.

One of the main goals of comparative pedagogy is that the student should get acquainted with the subjects and general education programs taught in relevant universities and colleges in other countries, as well as in the United States, and use the subjects and programs he deems necessary.

American higher education institutions annually award 540,000 junior specialist diplomas, 1.1 million bachelor's degrees, 400,000 master's degrees, 76,000 specialized diplomas, and 45,000 doctoral degrees (55, 13). It should be noted that in this country the training of specialists in biology, physics, mathematics and engineering - doctors of sciences - is given greater priority. It should be noted that about 50% of doctors of sciences working in leading American universities, ie specialists in engineering, are citizens of other countries.

As it is known, a new education system has been introduced in Azerbaijan for several years. All higher education institutions in the country already train specialists with bachelor's degrees, and great attention is paid to the training of masters. This structure of teaching, of course, is reflected in the development and implementation of programs.

The experience gained in conducting tests of university entrance exams in Azerbaijan is growing and enriching. Undoubtedly, greater success is expected in this area in the future. However, the experience gained clearly shows that students are not able to get acquainted with the test methods and rules in a short time. This is due to the fact that they do not have enough experience and skills to work on the test.

Looking at the current state of education in the United States, it is clear that this important problem is still solved in high school. Thus, students who want to enter colleges and universities in this country are still learning the rules of the test method in high school. Such application of the test has a positive effect on the increase of students' experience and skills in this field.

However, over the past 25 years, the results of such standard tests in the United States have been declining. Some researchers attribute this to the lack of an education system in the United States. American expert Bracey does not accept this position, showing that the percentage of high school students currently taking these tests is higher. If 25 years ago, a quarter of high school students were admitted to higher education, now more than 60 percent of high school students enter colleges and universities in the next academic year.

Thus, the advantages of the test in the field of education are manifested primarily in the admission to universities.

Research shows that as far back as the 1950s, less than half of all students accepted the education system in which they were awarded a certificate of secondary education. In the labor market, there was a huge demand for industrial workers, and there were many opportunities for low-skilled people.

Currently, the employment situation of the population has changed radically, and in connection with this, the need for education of students and society has changed.

Over the past 15 years, more than half of the additional funds allocated for education have been directed to "special education" programs. These programs stem from US efforts to create equal opportunities for its citizens.

According to experts, the majority of primary and secondary school students in the United States spoke English quite well. This allowed them to meet the requirements they encountered in the teaching process. Today, in some large states, especially California, Texas, and New York, 25 percent of students do not speak English well enough. This prevents them from mastering the basic curriculum. In schools in Los Angeles and a number of other major cities, students who do not speak English make up almost half of the total.

In other parts of the United States, there is a great variety of students. For example, in one of the schools around Washington, students speak 81 languages. According to the law, these students have the right to free education at school. The schools they attend must teach English to ensure that these children can attend regular classes.

However, there are other problems with these children, and their lack of knowledge of English does not end there. These students and their parents represent extremely diverse cultures. Therefore, the interaction and cooperation of the school, parents and children also creates certain problems.

Experience shows that interaction in such cases is one of the most important factors in the development of the educational process.

In a sense, this situation is also manifested in Azerbaijan. Thus, after gaining independence in Azerbaijan, some minorities, ethnic groups, national minorities raised the issue of organizing education in their national languages in primary school. Some have even created their own national alphabets. Inevitably, this situation makes us think: where should a child who is taught in his national language in primary school and then continue his education? Of course, it is very difficult to give a one-sided answer to this question. But

experience shows that if children study in the Azerbaijani language, where the vast majority of them are educated in our country, then they will have no difficulty in continuing their education in public life. They can continue their education on an equal footing as citizens of this country.

However, by studying in the national language, they may face great difficulties later. It is necessary to ensure that the national language does not hinder the overall development.

We must also note an important aspect here. We are not against education in the national language. Children must also learn the Azerbaijani language so that they can use it effectively in both primary and secondary school years, and ensure their development through this language.

As you can see, in some American states, if children do not know English, which creates difficulties and problems in secondary schools, in Azerbaijan we can see the opposite. In this regard, national characteristics and local conditions must be taken into account when using the experience gained in this field in American schools.

In the United States, the issue of putting schools at the disposal of the local community and the important role of schools in the organization of their leisure time has almost been resolved. The school plays a very important role in the development of the country as a cultural center. If before, ie before the Second World War, schools only educated children, acted as an educational center and their number was a minority in the country, since the 60s, the number of schools began to increase and their functions changed, in other words, became much richer. . Today, US schools are used not only for classes, but also as a place for meetings and various events to discuss issues of interest to the local population. After classes, various events are held in schools: community meetings, meetings of various clubs for adults, seniors' club, sports classes, etc. events are held.

This rule, this practice has not been applied in Azerbaijan. Only some socio-political events are held in our schools. Schools are widely used, especially during elections. Due to the widespread use of clubs in settlements and villages in the field of other events, it was preferred that schools operate only as educational institutions.

It seems that in the United States, because schools are under the auspices of local authorities, they are used not only as educational institutions, but also as cultural centers of the population. Local authorities also monitor the activities of schools. Jefferson, a former US president, not only acknowledged the importance of education in the overall development of society, but also argued that education should be the responsibility of local governments. However, local authorities should use only the authority given to them, ie not exceed their authority. Jefferson and his followers underestimated the role of central government in education. According to them, the central government should not force education to be accepted by the masses, but should create real conditions for people to come to education on the basis of their desires. Therefore, the US Constitution does not provide for education. In this document, the names of those responsible for education in the country are mentioned separately in the provision on the retention of powers. It is clear from this provision that the responsibility for education lies not with the US federal government, but with the states themselves. In the United States, there are 50 such states. Each state is responsible for the organization of educational activities within its territory. This means that schools are legally established by the states, control their activities and operate within the competence of local authorities. The U.S. government's interference in education only in matters within the competence of the federal government is possible only if the rights of national or racial minorities have been violated at the local level. In such cases, Washington is obliged to intervene immediately.

It should be noted that, unlike the United States, no cases of violation of the rights of national and racial minorities have been registered in secondary schools or universities in Azerbaijan. Because of in our country, both during the former Soviet Union and after gaining independence, no grounds have been created for such violations of rights and humiliation of the national dignity of citizens. The school has always been outside the policy of national discrimination, and all children, regardless of nationality or race, have been raised and educated in schools as equal citizens of the country. This policy continues today.

Unlike the United States, as it is known, the field of education in Azerbaijan is always in the focus of the state. The right to education is enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

However, we must keep in mind that the United States pursues its education policy only through the states. Back in the 1960s, when US President Johnson began implementing the Great Society program in the country, he envisioned the school life of the country in this program. The program included meals for students from poor families and funding for primary education. At that time, Washington allocated a lot of money to the states for this purpose.

By the way, it should be noted that since the late 50s in Azerbaijan, students have been provided with school uniforms and hot meals for a long time, including in primary schools and some upper grades.

Undoubtedly, these privileges were gradually abolished in connection with the improvement of living conditions. However, some schools still provide food to students, especially primary school children.

The Washington government provides an average of 7 percent of funding for local schools. The remaining funds for schools are allocated by the states and local authorities. Nevertheless, school circles in the country stand firm in guarding their powers and privileges. They see local control over schools as an integral part of US life. When the US government enacts a law on the condition of local schools, the introductory part of the law emphasizes the importance of local oversight and the need to maintain it. The implementation of local controls is appreciated and appreciated by many media outlets, as well as individual educators.

The work of school districts is supervised by state education councils. Each state has administrative departments responsible for education. The head of the state school education department, the inspector of the state education system, the commissioner for education work here elected Commissioner for Education in California and Florida. In other states, the governor is appointed by the state board of education. State governments set the rules for local school districts. They determine the number of school days per year, approve minimum state standards for teachers and administrators to be allowed to work, compile part of the curriculum, issue orders on which textbooks to use, and receive and distribute those textbooks from time to time. In addition, state governments set rules for awarding diplomas to graduates.

States also have the power to control financial resources. At the same time, they provide significant funding for local schools. The type and amount of local taxes are also determined by the state authorities.

As can be seen, the financing of the education system in the United States, as well as the design of the curriculum, is completely different from the general direction of development of the education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan. In our country, many issues related to education in the United States are solved by the states in a centralized manner, ie under the leadership of the Ministry of Education. Even though secondary schools in our country are directly managed by district education departments, local school circles in the United States are engaged in this work. If a local school district does not comply with one or another state law or regulation, the state government may reconsider allocating the necessary funds to that school district if it does not comply with one or another state law or regulation. In the mid-1980s, the Texas government passed a law that barred low-achieving students from engaging in extracurricular activities, such as playing sports or musical instruments. If the school district does not comply with this act, its head will not be imprisoned, but the school district under its jurisdiction may be deprived of state financial support, which is a real disaster. As a result of deprivation of financial assistance, all schools in the district may be closed. Although education councils and state special commissioners have broad official powers, all local school districts are fully independent. That is, school districts keep their own budgets, determine the goals of curricula, adopt regulations, hire and fire people. School districts are also responsible for the design, construction and proper maintenance of buildings. At the same time, most schools interact with relevant government agencies, local and federal officials. If there is any concern, then the school districts themselves speak on the issue. Even when bad weather is expected, the local leader has the right to close the school.

While the rights of teachers are protected by the state in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the teachers' union in the United States is involved. Decisions on teachers' salaries, working conditions, curricula and staffing are made at the same level. In America, much of the money needed for schooling comes from locals. They are supporters of local self-government, so they are very reluctant to intervene, either by the federal or state government. Over the past few decades, states have significantly increased their control over education as they play an active role in funding it. They have consistently sought to limit the time-tested tradition of local government.

In the 1980s, the rise of the "Education for All" movement in the United States led to the activation of some government officials. Even the US Secretary of Education made a report on "The nation is in danger" (Court on the education system: a strategy for the future / Per s engl., 1991.). The issues raised in this report were approved by government officials, state legislators and governors. It was recommended to pay special attention to the issues of attendance in education, at the same time it was shown that positive and negative incentives, rewards and punishments can be applied to change the student's behavior, but ultimately the student must be responsible for his own behavior.

Today, the United States pays great attention to the quality of the education system in order to maintain its leading and leading position in the world in the XXI century. Speaking to members of the National Association of African-American Journalists in Chicago in 2007, President George W. Bush said: "We will not be a united America in the 21st century without equal access to education and a high quality education system. We must create the opportunity for every American to receive the best education from the best teachers in the best educational institutions in the world. This means that we must have high standards, great aspirations

and a high degree of responsibility for each of us in the field of education.

Today, the backwardness of the US education system over Japan is already recognized at the state level. According to US Secretary of Education Arn Duncan, the main reason for this lag is that Japan pays more attention to science and mathematics in schools than in the United States. However, according to him, over the past decade, the United States has also made some progress in this area. According to the Minister of Education, over the past ten years, the level of knowledge of students in the field of natural sciences and mathematics has increased by about one point.

Although the United States is a leading and leading country in all areas, including education, it has kept this area in the spotlight. Civil servants, who pay great attention to the unique role of the education system in the further development of the country, consider the continuous improvement of this system as a matter of great state importance. In this respect, the education system of the liberated countries, as well as the Republic of Azerbaijan, can take a lot from the American education system. It is very important to take progressive steps for the development of our independent state.

References

1. Shorthand report of the XI Congress of Teachers of Azerbaijan "Chashyoglu, Baku, 1999, 293 pages.
2. Stenographic report of the XV Congress of Azerbaijani Teachers. Baku, 2018. - 14 p.
3. “Azerbaijan 2020: Vision for the Future” Development Concept, Baku, 2011.
4. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 67 "On the establishment of additional benefits and incentives for young professionals who graduated from higher and secondary vocational education institutions and began working in general education institutions." Baku, 2010.
5. State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku, 2013.
6. Ahmadov H.H. XIX century Azerbaijan enlightenment // Scientific works of the Institute of Educational Problems, №3, 2008. - 216-218
7. Changing educational landscapes: educational policies, schooling systems and higher education: a comparative perspective, selected papers from the 23rd CESE conference. Edited by Dimitris Mattheou (Dordrecht and London, Springer, 2010, 328 p.)
8. Schriewer J., Holmes B. Theories and methods in comparative education. - Frankfurt am Main & New York: Peter Lang, 1992
9. U.S. Society & Values, Electronic Journal of the Department of State, Vol. 5, No. 1, February 2000
10. U.S. Society & Values, Electronic Journal of the U.S. Information Agency, Vol. 9, No. 1, July 2014
11. В.В.Овчинников, Корни дуба (Впечатления и размышления об Англии и англичанах), 1980 (<http://www.e-reading.club/book.php?book=42483>)
12. Суд над системой образования: стратегия на будущее / Пер с англ. М., 1991.